

Synthesis and Characterization of Copper(II) and Nickel(II) Complexes with Schiff Bases derived from Aromatic Diamines and Heterocyclic Aldehydes

(MS.) MINATI SATPATHY and B. PRADHAN*

Department of Chemistry, Regional Engineering College, Rourkela-769 008

Manuscript received 27 June 1997, revised 28 November 1997, accepted 30 April 1998

Chelating ligands derived from thiophene-2-aldehyde and *o*-phenylenediamine (talophen) or *m*-phenylenediamine (talmphen) have been synthesized. The complexes of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} have been isolated. [Cu(talophen)₂]Cl₂, [Cu(talmphen)₂]Cl₂, [Ni(talophen)₂]Cl₂, [Ni(talmphen)₂]Cl₂ are diamagnetic and square-planar. Other Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes show μ_{eff} indicative of their distorted octahedral or octahedral nature.

A number of Schiff base complexes of transition metal atoms have been reported due to their multifaceted applications. The present communication deals with the coordinating behaviour of thiophene-2-aldehyde derivatives of *o*-phenylenediamine and *m*-phenylenediamine with Ni^{II} and Cu^{II}. The nature of bonding and the possible structures of the complexes are discussed. An attempt has been made to study the preference and stabilization of coordination number and stereochemistry by Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} when provided with Schiff base environment containing N and S as donor sites.

Results and Discussion

Ir spectra : The ir spectra of both the ligands exhibited strong bands around 1630 (C=N) and ~700 cm⁻¹ (thiophene C-S). Both showed sharp bands at 3340–3330 and 3120–3100 cm⁻¹, assigned to asymmetric and symmetric stretching of NH₂ group respectively¹.

The ir spectra of all the complexes (Table 1) showed a downward shift of about 5–15 cm⁻¹ in the $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ vibrations, which is due to the reduction of electron density in azomethine links. The $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ band observed at 700–725 cm⁻¹ in all the complexes shows the coordination through sulphur of thiophene ring. Further, the free ligands displayed a band at 1580 cm⁻¹ (NH₂ deformation) which was absent in the complexes. In all the complexes, the ν_{NH_2} bands remained unaltered at 3340–3330 and 3120–3100 cm⁻¹ which shows the non-involvement of amino group in the complex formation. The C–S stretching frequency was shifted to a higher value on account of an increased $d\pi-d\pi$ contribution between sulphur atom and the ring π -system². In the present case, the band at 700–725 cm⁻¹ (C–S) are indicative of Schiff base bonded through sulphur atom with non-involvement of amino group in the complex formation³. These data indicate that the ligands are coordinated through nitrogen atom of C=N and sulphur atom of thiophene.

In [M(SB₁)₂(CH₃COO)₂] and [M(SB₂)(CH₃COO)₂] complexes, additional bands observed at ~1515, ~1430, ~1335 and ~700 cm⁻¹ can be assigned to $\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{COO})$, $\nu_{\text{sym}}(\text{COO})$, $\delta(\text{CH}_3)$ and $\delta(\text{COO})$ respectively indicating

the presence of acetate ion in the coordination sphere⁴. In [M(SB₁)₂(NO₃)₂] and [M(SB₂)₂(NO₃)₂] complexes, additional bands observed at ~1520 and ~1300 cm⁻¹ are for ν_{asym} and ν_{sym} respectively. The absence of ν_3 band of ionic nitrate around 1360 cm⁻¹ and the presence of strong ν_{asym} and ν_{sym} bands suggest the unidentate nature of coordinated nitrate group⁴.

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES*

Compounds (Colour/M.p. ^o C)	Metal % : Found(Calcd.)	Λ_m $\Omega^{-1}\text{cm}^2\text{mol}^{-1}$	μ_{eff} B.M.
Talophen(SB ₁) (Green, 51)	—	—	—
Talmphen(SB ₂) (Brown, 52)	—	—	—
[Cu(SB ₁) ₂]Cl ₂ (Green, 209)	11.23 (11.79)	132	dia
[Cu(SB ₁) ₂ (CH ₃ COO) ₂] (Green, 220)	10.33 (10.85)	20	1.92
[Cu(SB ₁) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂] (Green, 280)	10.52 (10.74)	22	1.93
[Cu(SB ₂) ₂]Cl ₂ (Brown, 220)	11.41 (11.79)	135	dia
[Cu(SB ₂) ₂ (CH ₃ COO) ₂] (Green, 230)	10.52 (10.85)	18	1.89
[Cu(SB ₂) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂] (Green, 270)	10.31 (10.74)	24	1.95
[Ni(SB ₁) ₂]Cl ₂ (Green, 290)	10.64 (10.99)	137	dia
[Ni(SB ₁) ₂ (CH ₃ COO) ₂] (Brown, 300)	10.98 (11.25)	25	3.4
[Ni(SB ₁) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂] (Green, 310)	9.78	21	3.1
[Ni(SB ₂) ₂]Cl ₂ (Brown, 295)	10.72 (10.99)	138	dia
[Ni(SB ₂) ₂ (CH ₃ COO) ₂] (Green, 310)	10.82 (11.25)	25	3.4
[Ni(SB ₂) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂] (Green, 315)	9.81 (10.00)	20	3.3

*All compounds gave satisfactory S and Cl (where applicable) analyses.

Electronic spectra and magnetic moment : The four coordinated complexes of [M(SB₁)₂]Cl₂ and [M(SB₂)₂]Cl₂ may have either a tetrahedral or a square-planar geometry. The regular tetrahedral complexes of Cu^{II} show no *d-d* ab-

sorption bands⁶ in the region 10000–20000 cm^{-1} . The spectra of $[\text{Cu}(\text{SB}_1)_2]\text{Cl}_2$ and $[\text{Cu}(\text{SB}_2)_2]\text{Cl}_2$ displayed a band around 13500 cm^{-1} . Hence, they are definitely not tetrahedral. Further, the position of this band around 13500 cm^{-1} is in agreement with that generally observed for square-planar complexes. Electronic spectral bands in $[\text{Cu}(\text{SB}_1)_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]$, $[\text{Cu}(\text{SB}_2)_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]$, $[\text{Cu}(\text{SB}_1)_2(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2]$ and $[\text{Cu}(\text{SB}_2)_2(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2]$ complexes have been observed around 16660 which is indicative of their distorted octahedral structure⁵. The four complexes of $[\text{Ni}(\text{SB}_1)_2]\text{Cl}_2$ and $[\text{Ni}(\text{SB}_2)_2]\text{Cl}_2$ do not show any band below 10000 cm^{-1} , which rules out the probability of tetrahedral geometry for the complexes⁵. A broad band observed at ~ 21200 for these complexes corresponds to the transition ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1T_{2g}$ and is suggestive of square-planar geometry. The spectra of $[\text{Ni}(\text{SB}_1)_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]$, $[\text{Ni}(\text{SB}_2)_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]$, $[\text{Ni}(\text{SB}_1)_2(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2]$, $[\text{Ni}(\text{SB}_2)_2(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2]$ exhibit bands at 10400–10000, 15300–14000 and 24500–24200 cm^{-1} corresponding to the transitions ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$ (ν_1), ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ (ν_2) and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3) respectively, expected for octahedral Ni^{II} complexes⁶. $[\text{M}(\text{SB}_1)_2]\text{Cl}_2$ and $[\text{M}(\text{SB}_2)_2]\text{Cl}_2$ complexes are found to be diamagnetic which is consistent with the square-planar geometry. The magnetic moment values of other Cu^{II} complexes are found to be 1.89–1.95 B.M. which indicate that all these complexes are paramagnetic as expected for $3d^9$ configuration⁷. The μ_{eff} values of rest of the Ni^{II} complexes are found to be in the range 3.1–3.4 B.M. These values are consistent with the values reported for octahedral Ni^{II} complexes⁸.

Analytical, molar conductance and magnetic susceptibility data are given in the Table 1. Complexes of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} formed with thiophene-2-aldehyde, *o*-phenylenediamine and *m*-phenylenediamine, i.e. $[\text{Cu}(\text{talphen})_2]\text{Cl}_2$, $[\text{Cu}(\text{talmphen})_2]\text{Cl}_2$ have 1 : 2 stoichiometry which is quite consistent with their high conductance values showing the electrolytic nature of the complexes. The rest of the complexes have 1 : 1 stoichiometry and they are non-electrolyte as inferred from their low conductance values. All the complexes are quite stable and have high decomposition temperature. These complexes are soluble in DMF.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of AnalaR grade.

Preparation of ligands : Thiophene-2-aldehyde (2.24 g, 0.02 mol) was mixed with *o*-phenylenediamine or *m*-phenylenediamine (2.16 g, 0.02 mol) at 0–5°. The mixture was stirred for 0.5 h and the resulting deep coloured Schiff base appeared as oil which solidified gradually in 3–4 days

Preparation of complexes : The Schiff base (0.02 mol) dissolved in DMF was mixed separately with the ethanolic solution of metal(II) chloride/nitrate/acetate (0.01 mol) in 2 : 1 ratio. The reaction mixture was kept over a water-bath for ~ 2 h. After keeping it for 2–3 days, the separated metal chelates were washed with ethanol, ether and dried under reduced pressure

Metals were estimated by standard methods⁹. Chlorine was estimated as silver chloride and sulphur as BaSO_4 . IR spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu 408 spectrophotometer and electronic spectra on a Elico CL-54 spectrophotometer. Conductance was measured in $\sim 10^{-3}$ M solution of DMF with a Systronics 303 conductivity meter. Magnetic susceptibility was measured at room temperature by a Gouy balance. Diamagnetic corrections were made by Pascal's constants¹⁰.

References

- 1 J V QUAGLIANO, G V SVATOS and B C CURRAN, *Anal Chem*, 1958, **26**, 29
- 2 S C MAHAPATRA and D V R RAO, *J Indian Chem Soc*, 1980, **57**, 262
- 3 R N DASH and D V R RAO, *J Indian Chem Soc*, 1974, **51**, 787
- 4 K NAKAMOTO, "Infrared and Raman Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Wiley, New York, 1978
- 5 A B P LEVER, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1968
- 6 A B P LEVER, *J Chem Educ*, 1968, **43**, 711
- 7 R L DUTTA and M M HOSSAIN, *Indian J Chem, Sect A*, 1984, **23**, 30
- 8 F A COTTON and G WILKINSON, "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry", 3rd ed, Wiley-Eastern, New Delhi, 1979
- 9 A I VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", ELBS, London, 1961
- 10 P W SELWOOD, "Magnetochemistry", 2nd ed, 1956